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Zolotukhina N., Markhaychuk N., Tarasov V., Chadaeva K. Collage of Sergey Paradzhanov: features of the periodization of creativity.

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The work on the film “Shadows of forgotten ancestors” displays the second stage in the artist’s artistic biography. During this period, Paradzhanov already found himself in the collage genre. The collage of Paradzhanov acts as a directing instrument, and at the same time it acts as a completely independent artistic creativity. Probably at this time Paradzhanov understands the special role of the collage in creative filmmaking process.

The third stage is connected with Paradzhanov’s undeserved imprisonment. All this complex of causes determines peculiarities of formal-stylistic and compositional construction of works of the “prison” period. They are mostly concise, they do not contain his typical baguettes and they are aimed at solving traditional circle of themes: family, freedom, love, death.

The fourth stage in the artistic creativity of the master begins after his release from prison (1977) and lasts until the first personal exhibition in Tbilish House of Cinema that took place in 1985. A number of researchers of Sergey Paradzhanov’s creativity consider this period to be “the blossoming period of his fine art.” The fifth stage is the most productive stage for Paradzhanov the artist. It lasts from 1985 until his death in 1990.

Series of collage works “Several episodes from the life of Gioconda” deserves special attention. The analyzed sources and research materials allow us to assert that the overall evolution of Sergey Paradzhanov’s collage takes place in several stages.

Keywords: kolazh, Sergiy Paradzhanov, nonconformism, post-modernism.

Золотухіна Н., Мархайчук Н., Тарасов В., Чадаєва К. Колаж Сергія Параджанова: особливості періодизації. Колаж супроводжує творчість Сергія Параджанова практично із самого початку його мистецького шляху, а з сер. 1960-х рр. стає своєрідною «паралельною режисурою» його кінематографії. У такому контексті автори статті розглядають п’ять основних періодів.

Перший етап пов’язаний зі становленням Параджанова як режисера та художника (сер. 1950-х — сер. 1960-х). Роботи цього часу засвідчують пошук свого творчого обличчя, появу специфічної манери колажування. Робота над стрічкою «Тіні забутих предків» відкриває другий етап. Колаж виступає як інструментарій режисури і водночас як цілком самостійна художня творчість. Третій етап пов’язаний із «тюремним періодом». Це визначає особливості формально-стилістичної та композиційної побудови творів: вони лаконічні та спрямовані на розв’язання іншого кола тем: родина, свобода, кохання, смерть. Четвертий етап триває від звільнення у 1977 році до першої персональної виставки у Тбіліському будинку кіно (1985). Активність митця як колажиста пояснюється

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COLLAGE OF SERGEY PARADZHANOV: FEATURES OF THE PERIODIZATION OF CREATIVITY

відсутністю робіт у кіно. П’ятий етап є найбільш продуктивним (1985–1990). Це завершальний акорд у творчості майстра. Окремою сторінкою цього періоду є серія колажних робіт «Кілька епізодів із життя Джоконди».

Визначені нами періоди у творчості майстра відтворюють загальну еволюцію колажу Сергія Параджанова як синтетичного, універсального мистецтва.

Ключові слова: колаж, Сергій Параджанов, нонконформізм, постмодернізм.

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Перший етап пов’язаний зі становленням Параджанова як режисера і художника (сер. 1950-х — сер. 1960-х). Роботи цього періоду свідчать про пошук свого творчого обличчя, появу специфічної манери колажування. Робота над фільмом «Тіні забутих предків» відкриває другий етап. Колаж виступає як інструментарій режисури і одночасно як цілком самостійне художнє творчість. Третій етап пов’язаний із «тюремним періодом». Це визначає особливості формально-стилістичного і композиційного побудови творів: вони лаконічні і направлені на рішення іншого кола тем: родина, свобода, любов, смерть. Четвертий етап починається після звільнення в 1977 році до першої персональної виставки в Тбіліському будинку кіно (1985). Активність художника як колажиста пояснюється відсутністю робіт у кіно. П’ятий етап — найбільш результативний (1985–1990). Це завершальний акорд у творчості майстра. Окремою сторінкою цього періоду є серія робіт «Кілька епізодів із життя Джоконди».

Таким образом, обозначенные нами периоды в творчестве мастера воссоздают общую эволюцию коллажа Сергея Параджанова как синтетического, универсального искусства.

Ключевые слова: коллаж, Сергей Параджанов, нонконформизм, постмодернизм.

Problem statement. Research of creativity of the world-famous director and artist Sergey Paradzhanov has been going on for several decades. The witches’ films have long been included in the treasury of world cinema, and about Sergei Paradzhanov has been filmed at least a dozen documentary films. In this context, Paradzhanov’s artistic work is still in the background. The collage is an integral and extremely important part of the artist’s overall creativity. The collage began to determine the originality of the artistic style of the artist from the very beginning of his professional work.

The Collage works make a significant layer in creative work of the master. The collage accompanies Paradzhanov from the very beginning of his artistic path, and from the middle of 1960s it became a kind of “parallel direction” (in the words of V. Katanyan) of his cinematographic art.

Thus, the analysis of Sergei Paradzhanov’s collages in the context of the development of the visual culture of Ukraine in the second half of the twentieth century is an urgent need for modern Ukrainian art.

The present state of research of the problem remains focused on the historical and cultural direction. Attention to the artist’s creativity comes from the late 1980s and early 1990s. Nevertheless, the professional research of Sergei Paradzhanov’s creativity began actively in the 1990’s, after the death of the artist. Directly the problem of artistic works by Paradzhanov was dedicated to L. Grigoryan, V. Katanyan [5], M. Oganessian [7], O. Petrova [8], L. Lemesheva, T. Bodnarchuk [2].

The **main task** of the study of collage in the work of Sergey Paradzhanov as an organic component of the development of visual culture of Ukraine in the second half of the twentieth century.

Presentation of the main study. In general, analyzed sources and research materials allow us to assert that general evolution of Paradzhanov’s collage takes place in several stages.

The first stage is connected with the formation of Sergey Paradzhanov as a director and an artist. This period is less investigated, because there is a lack of sources for comprehensive analysis. In addition, many early works of the master were lost. Conditional chronology of this stage is the middle of the 1950s and the 1960s. At that period Sergey Paradzhanov was criticized as a director a lot. He even falls into the list of the weakest directors of the film studio named after A. Dovzhenko. The artistic environment of this time does not know Paradzhanov as an artist. At the same time, this period is important for the formation of artistic style of the master.

Being a student, Sergey Paradzhanov went through a typical learning process at art school to become a director. It also affected the features of his future creative style. For example, in one of the interviews, Paradzhanov recalls Igor Savchenko, who was his teacher at the All-Union State Institute of Cinematography (VGIK). He “forced students to draw, express their thoughts in a plastic form using a pencil”. This experience was one of the most valuable for the master [9].

In memoirs V. Bazhenov notes that the absence of special artistic education is not a negative feature of Sergey Paradzhanov. On the contrary, classical education could prevent him from being an artist: “He is organic, like Pirosmanni. Expressive lines of his drawings are as professional and perfect, as Picasso’s lines” [3].

The works of this time testify the search for their creative personality and the formation of his specific style of artistic expression. Probably, the transition from a picture to a collage takes place under the influence of scenario and cinematographic reflections.

V. Katanyan says that he heard “the word ‘collage’ from him for the first time, probably, about thirty years ago (that is, in the first half of the 1960s. – *Author’s note*). Actually nobody was interested in it at that period of time. His works were completely individual and did not resemble the collages of Matisse or Delone, Hofmeister or Prevert, Altman or Stepanova. They had nothing in common with photomontage of Zhytomyrskiy or Rodchenko” [5, p. 83].

It was in the 1960s that he showed his worth and interest to the subject world. Many of his friends and memoirists emphasize that Sergey Paradzhanov was born and brought up in a family of antique dealer. According to his own memoirs, “there were wonderful things at home; they came and then ... they disappeared. Tables and armchairs, Rococo dressers, antique cameos, vases and gorgeous oriental blankets ... I was very attached to them, and the more I grew up, the more I wanted to communicate with them, as if with living creatures” [7, p. 34].

The work on the film “Shadows of forgotten ancestors” displays the second stage in the artist’s artistic biography. During this period, Sergey Paradzhanov already found himself in the collage genre. But it was not perceived as an independent genre of fine art by artistic academic community at that time.

The appeal to “Shadows of Forgotten Ancestors” written by M. Kotsiubynsky and cinematographic reading of this work at the intersection of ethnography of the 19th century and modernism of the 20th century were fully in line with the spirit of the time and artistic searches for the generation of the sixties. Without realizing the character of time of “sixties”, one can hardly adequately assess Sergey Paradzhanov’s film and its historical and cultural context. In addition, “Shadows of forgotten ancestors” were created in cooperation with such Ukrainian artists of the 1960s as G. Yakutovich and camera operator Yu. Illienko.

During this period, the collage of Sergey Paradzhanov acts as a directing instrument, and at the same time it acts as a completely independent artistic creativity. The tremendous success of the film “Shadows of Forgotten Ancestors” became so famous milestone in the formation of the master, which was reflected in collage works of this time. Actually, this is about planned series called “Farewell to Ukraine” and an ironic portrait of Y. Illienko as “the Emperor”. Paradzhanov was able to realize it partially only in prison.

Probably at this time Sergey Paradzhanov understands the special role of the collage in creative filmmaking process. His specific way to play with certain elements of action or visual representation of the image through artistic possibilities of a collage work was maturing.

That is why most researchers see “dramatic works” in Sergey Paradzhanov’s collage works. “The master creates a plane cinematography” using magazine cuts, cloth pieces, pieces of glass, feathers, leaves and flowers [1, p. 162]. We would like to emphasize that this period is connected both with Ukraine and with Armenia, where the artist was

invited in 1966 after the closure of the film “Kiev frescoes”.

The collage “The Emperor Y. Ilyenko” is characteristic for this period (1966), which has several iconic accents and layers. An obvious game of the words “operator/emperor” (it should be reminded that Y. Ilyenko worked with Paradzhanov on the film “Shadows of forgotten ancestors”) is not just a good hint of the important role of young operator in the cinematographic success of the film, but also it stresses the character features and working manners of Y. Ilyenko. Sometimes it led to conflict situations with the master on the shooting stage.

The collage has several characteristic compositional features. A photograph of a man’s profile (most likely, a printout of a Roman sculptural portrait) is the central figure of the work. It forms plane presentation of the “canvas”, on which “slipping” down female profile is placed by means of two vertical fragments. The collage materials are arranged in layers. Scorched and torn edges of the collage form the intentional textural “negligence” that is typical for Paradzhanov’s artistic works of this period. Sculptural (but quite anatomical) outlines of male and female profiles appear in unequal, wavy pieces of collage material (photo paper, wallpaper, canvas), which are delineated by a rectangular baguette in usual style of Paradzhanov.

Colour scheme of the work is two-staged: an olive-body colour of woman’s profile is in harmony with the wallpaper background; and, white profile of the “emperor” is performed by wide strokes of white paint in the upper and lower parts of the “canvas” through a layer of collage material. Thanks to these colours, black background of a printed photo of a male profile organizes compositional center of the work, dividing two colour schemes into layers.

Purely Paradzhanov’s feature of sign-symbolic expression deserves special attention. A collage is a “compressed film.” Potentially it has several ways of reading (male/female, white/black, elite/mass, etc.). Probably, the fact that the birthday of Ilyenko (July 18) is not the coincidence. It is an allusion to the legendary act of the Roman Emperor Nero, who destroys part of Rome by intentional arson on the night of July 18 to July 19 in 64 AD. Unfortunately, we do not have either memoirs or research evidence that would confirm this assumption. But peculiarities of reading of the whole artistic work are self-evident. Burned edges of wallpaper layer are body colour and printouts are black. Paradzhanov summarizes it using two characteristic accents: the first one is cigarette burning of the profile fragment of the “emperor” in the center of the image and the second one is dark red ribbon in the background, to which the overall movement of the composition and the look of Y. Ilyenko are directed.

The third stage is connected with Sergey Paradzhanov’s undeserved imprisonment, which became an enormous test for the master. At the same time this fact finally determined duality of his work: since his release from the prison, Paradzhanov the painter is known not less than Paradzhanov the director. The artist noted it in a letter to his friend: “I left

my energy in prison, where I became an artist. And I brought 800 works from there ... I survived in a prison camp creating one collage per day” [7, p. 34].

It is clear that from the objective circumstances of this period, both in direct and in the figurative sense, it is the least cinematic in the work of the master. Sergey Parajanov completely immersed in the part of his own creative nature, which was the only possible way in conditions of physical imprisonment.

Collage works of this time were made mainly of two types of material: blank postcards sent by his wife and friends and junk that was available to Sergey Paradzhanov in his local, closed environment. The master had difficulties about technical techniques of collage, because only scissors (not always) and glue were his available instruments.

All this complex of causes determines peculiarities of formal-stylistic and compositional construction of works of the “prison” period. They are mostly concise, they do not contain his typical baguettes and they are aimed at solving traditional circle of themes: family, freedom, love, death.

Epistolary nature of collage works of this time is another distinctive feature of his creativity. Sergey Paradzhanov prepared collages as fragments of correspondence with friends and family. As a rule, such works represent one complex with content and mood of the letter.

Specific prison life encourages the master to make interesting experiments. Then Sergey Paradzhanov transforms them both in filmmaking process and collage art. So, well-known “Paradzhanov’s thalers” (executed on covers of milk bottles “coinage”), gave rise to a “heraldic series”. Some of them were used for the film festival winners in Rimini and for the logo of Kiev Film Festival “Molodist” [7, p. 34].

In our view, Paradzhanov’s works of this time can be combined into one cycle. It is connected with a number of circumstances:

1) Prison period, which deeply influenced on creative mood and the choice of subjects of works as evidenced by his correspondence with family and friends;

2) Peculiarities of prison life circumstances, which determined the nature of collage materials; famous Paradzhanov’s “rubbish” was not the result of his free choice, but it was rather “superimposed” by surrounding situation;

3) Influence of prison camp environment on S. Paradzhanov, which was significantly different from his usual circle of communication, as it was repeatedly mentioned by the master himself and his biographers;

4) Impossibility to create artistic works and use them freely; prisoners, prison guards, friends and relatives that were far away from him represented S. Paradzhanov’s audience during this period; and if the first feature in most cases meant the subject of works and their figurative-stylistic orientation, then the second one predetermined a whole range of formal and compositional solutions. Since the artist had to create artistic works in the correspondence format with corresponding features of the sheet size, materials and indispensable textual accompaniment.

The most typical examples of such works are "Letters from the prison", "Flowers from the prison", "Collage from the prison", "Self-portrait from the prison", etc. S. Paradzhanov did not make sense to name them because of their epistolary nature. Such collages were part of the letter text. They formed a common mood and visually reproduced certain aspects of written material.

Among works of this, conditionally speaking, "prison cycle", we should mention two unnamed collages executed on the back side of the air mail postcards. The master was greatly limited in material and used blue-black border of postal printing as an imaginary border, filling cut elements of the "old painting" with a herbarium and droplets of resin.

Drawings-collages under the title "The Parable of a Son" represent another cycle of prison series. S. Paradzhanov sent them to various addressees during 1977. In visual heritage of the master, these works are the most minimalistic. Frank hints of biblical history from the New Testament are expressed by means of symbolism of "ihtios" by S. Paradzhanov. They are anagrams of the first letters of the name of Jesus Christ, which at the same time coincide with the Greek word "fish". Subsequently, the master repeatedly turned to this symbol in a number of other collage works.

Two collage works named "Sprats" are an example of the prison camp environment influence on the master. According to S. Paradzhanov's friends the collage "Marriage Night of the Japanese Emperor" was created by the order of "prison lads".

From the formal-stylistic point of view, the prison cycle of S. Paradzhanov's works goes far beyond the time of the master's stay in prison camps. For example, the collage ensemble of 1978 "A Thief Will Never Become a Laundress" is executed by the director after his release from the prison, but it is difficult enough to consider the plot itself and its stylistic features separately from the "prison camp" legacy of the master.

The collage depicts Paradzhanov himself, who squeezes raised up broom with his hands. In the upper left corner of the work, a black mitten stretches to the chain, which "holds" the figure in the plane of the round wooden structure. The name of the work is a well-known thief's proverb and Paradzhanov "shows" it as an expression of his own creative freedom in the state of physical imprisonment. According to L. Abramyan, the idea of this work was born from the real case. It happened as a result of S. Paradzhanov's conflict with the guard, who made a comment to the master that he was sweeping the floor of the prison camp "half-heartedly". In response, S. Paradzhanov set fire to the broom [4, p. 55–56].

The fourth stage in the artistic creativity of the master begins after his release from prison (1977) and lasts until the first personal exhibition in Tbilish House of Cinema that took place in 1985. The first phase of this stage is a kind of inertia of the previous period of imprisonment: Paradzhanov has not expressed emotions and topics of being in prison yet. In this or another sense his collage works relate to prison camp experience.

A number of researchers of Sergey Paradzhanov's creativity consider this period to be "the blossoming period of his fine art." In opinion of some researches this fact can be explained by the lack of filmmaking work ("doomed to unemployment artist tried to translate all his fantasies into scenarios and collages") [7, p. 34], while other researchers emphasized the emergence of a number of new possibilities for creation because Paradzhanov had access to a wider range of materials and techniques.

The first personal exhibition at Tbilisi House of Cinema in 1985 is the final chord of this stage and at the same time it is an important milestone in the artist's creative biography. The exhibition was called "Ball in the studio of a filmmaker" and the premiere of the new film created by Sergey Paradzhanov "The Legend of Suram Fortress" was held in the program of its opening.

V. Katanyan left several characteristic descriptions of works of the master. In his opinion, they formed the basis of exposition and represented Sergey Paradzhanov as an artist. "Ungracious work to describe the painting, but I will try. Here's a big cardboard, on which there is the officer's straps, scattering golden coins and paper money, from which instead of the portrait of the emperor looks beautiful and threatening face of the old one. ... In the middle of the hall there was his self-portrait. It was a figure in medieval short warm overcoat, and the crown of the hat was made of a cage where two real parrots cherished. ... And I see at the exhibition: a self-portrait doll, where a gray, thick beard is made of ... a brush for washing bottles; an old Inna's glove on which Paradzhanov the king is disposed with surgical precision, and the king of the state holds his favorite pomegranate in his hand; an elephant's head was built from the torn suitcase: belts and buckles formed its eyes, ears and trunk, and the name is 'India welcomes KoraTsereteli'. ... I recall at random his collages and compositions with dolls: 'Tsar David in the bath', 'The thief will never become a laundress', 'Retro', 'Childhood of Genghis Khan', Lilia Brick, 'Danaia', 'Lermontov' ... When he was offered to extend the exhibition's term, he replied: 'No, let the legend remain.' And it remained" [5, p. 82–83].

According to Georgian artist R. Condahsazov, the exhibition really did a "tremendous impression" and resembled an unprecedented "pilgrimage". However, Sergey Paradzhanov emphasized in his personal conversations that it was rather a director's event, rather than an art exhibition [6].

The fifth stage is the most productive stage for Paradzhanov the artist. It lasts from 1985 until his death in 1990.

Series of collage works "Several episodes from the life of Gioconda" deserves special attention. The first work displays "Crying Gioconda", which was made in a prison camp in 1977 and sent to V. Katanyan in a letter [9].

Subsequently, Paradzhanov develops this idea to develop the series, which in general, as it has been already noted, contains 12 works. The image of Gioconda is used by the artist to create different situations and sentiments: men and women who are

portrayed in the profile look at us by Mona Lisa's eyes ("The Last Supper", "Dante", "Two Profiles"); from a distant renaissance woman, Gioconda becomes a harlot ("The Harlot No 1", "The Harlot No 2"); falls into hell ("Gioconda in the Hell of Bosch"), in the company of V. Vysotsky and M. Plisetskaya.

V. Katanyan retells Paradzhanov's remark about the series idea: "Do you know why this (Gioconda. – *Author's note*) is so variable? One day, during the heat we put off our shirts and worked naked to the waist, then I saw tattooed Gioconda on the back of one zek. When he raised his hands, the skin stretched out, and Gioconda laughed, when he bent over she was sad and when he scratched behind his ear she blinked with her eyes. She constantly made faces to us" [7, p. 34].

According to the performing technique and application of artistic principles of collage work, the series "Several episodes from the life of Gioconda" is divided into two groups.

The first group includes the work with frottage technique, where Leonardo's "Mona Lisa" acts as an artistic whole, against which the master forms layers of collage material. Sometimes, Paradzhanov uses one more or several reproductions of Gioconda as a kind of collage elements. In other cases, the reproduction becomes a peculiar background for decoupage or ensemble creation. In the picture "The Harlot No 1" the master uses a graphic retouching technique, with a black marker or a pencil.

The second group of works is tied to an integral whole by common feature of fragmentation of Mona Lisa's reproductions without preserving the author's compositional idea. The classic (traditional) collage technique used by the master in this case is not aimed at dialogue with Leonardo's art techniques, but, rather, serves as Paradzhanov's central formal-stylistic method. In works of this group, Gioconda is used by the master as a kind of "scrap-set" (face, elements, clothes, hands), which forms a qualitatively new reading of the work in a different combinatorics.

For example, if "The Harlot No 1" and "The Harlot No 2" is a clear hint at reflections of Leonardo da Vinci himself about the work, then "The Last Supper" and "Dante" act as independent authorial reflections on other topics and artistic situations that are not specific to any context of Mona Lisa. It is significant that Paradzhanov retains the second plan of Leonardo's "Gioconda" in the first case, moving his own collage space into the lower horizontal third and accentuating the upper part of the work with fragmentary decor (for example, "Pieta").

In our opinion, stylistic features of the series "Several episodes from the life of Gioconda" should be considered as a combination of artistic expressions, typical for cinema, with features of visual collage directly in pure Paradzhanov's aesthetics. The master uses mainly fragmentation of the face and hands of Leonardo's "Mona Lisa" to create his own formal-stylistic whole. From the standpoint of the morphology of collage creation, this feature is consistent with the principle of collage reversibility, where the problem of "recognition" of the source material is the basic condition for an aesthetic conflict.

In our view, it is planned as a kind of not the main feature of the whole series by the author.

Let's assume that from the point of view of technical and technological properties of series creation, the master had to rely on widely printed at the same time fully recognizable artistic image in the Soviet printing press. As previously noted, the idea of creating a collage based on Leonardo's "Mona Lisa" was born during his stay in prison. The opportunity itself to present a female image (a frontal figure with a specific hand and soft facial features) as a material for collage opened many opportunities for Paradzhanov. Thus, the Soviet printing polygraphy of the 1970s and 1980s duplicated many of these works (for example, works of O. Deineka, Yuri Shilov, etc.). Postcards with images of a Soviet woman were massive and accessible material. However, Paradzhanov chooses "Mona Lisa" as a certain "generalized portrait of all mankind" (according to A. Agranat), thus destroying all probable ideological and conformist obstacles. According to opinion of his friends and colleagues, reproductions of old masters were among those "subjects and objects" that formed Paradzhanov's "everyday life". Let us dare to assume that premature death of the master in 1990 interrupted the whole period of Paradzhanov's creative dialogue with "great art" through household and apparently petty objects of surrounding everyday life.

From the compositional point of view, the series is "sculpted" by almost "sculptural" (voluminous-plastic) means: collage elements model artistic integrity of the image in several variants: the chiasmic ("The Harlot No 2"), the frontal-plane ("Crying Gioconda"), and accented ("Pieta"). At the same time, Paradzhanov put all twelve works of the series in heavy, mostly openwork baguettes. In some works, the space of a baguette is used as a canvas plane (for example, "The Last Supper"). As previously noted, "framing" of his own works is a characteristic feature of master's aesthetic style. But the series demonstrates particular compositional integrity of this "non-artistic" element. Traditionally, baguettes tend to interior rather than to painting, they are intended for harmonious integration of one kind of art (painting) into another artistic plane (interior art). Paradzhanov's plasticity of the work's framing destroys this tradition, continuing the compositional movement of the work outside the conditional "canvas" (for example, "Dante", "Triple Portrait", etc.).

We can assume that the place in the format of a series is determined by generalized artistic whole, which includes the shape and size of the baguette. Additionally, this is evidenced by the use of S. Paradzhanov's baguette plane to change compositional accents in replicas and copies of the series works.

In 1988 and 1989 there are two more personal exhibitions of Sergey Paradzhanov in Yerevan, at the Museum of Folk Art of Armenia. Exhibitions were called "Visit to the filmmaker's studio" and they became a true representation of Paradzhanov the artist.

It was during this period that Sergey Paradzhanov experiments with collage of old masters' works, giving new interpretations to famous works.

Conclusions. The analyzed sources and research materials allow us to assert that the overall evolution of Sergey Paradzhanov's collage takes place in several stages.

The first stage (from the middle of the 1950s to the middle of the 1960's) was associated with the formation of Paradzhanov as a director and artist.

The second stage (from the middle of the 1960 – to 1977) in the artist's biography is marked by the work on the film "Shadows of forgotten ancestors". During this period, the collage acts as a directing instrument for Sergey Paradzhanov. At the same time it acts as a completely independent artistic creativity.

The third stage (1973–1977) is connected with the prison term of Sergey Paradzhanov. It became an enormous test for the master and at the same time it finally determined the multidirectionality of his work. Since he was released from prison, Paradzhanov the painter is known no less than Paradzhanov the director.

The fourth stage (1977–1985) in the artistic creativity of the master begins after his release from prison and continues until the first personal exhibition at the House of Cinema in Tbilisi in 1985. It is precisely this period that is considered to be the heyday of his fine art.

The fifth stage is the most productive for Paradzhanov the artist. It lasts from 1985 until the time of his death in 1990. This period is marked by creation of the main program works of the master; serial work is a characteristic feature of Paradzhanov's creative style.

Perspective of the further development of the topic. There is a further prospect for the study of the artistic language of the works of Paradzhanov. Also of interest is the analysis of stylistic and compositional solutions of the artist's early works.

Bibliography:

1. Асалханова М. В. Коллаж как искусство: техника, история, художники [Текст] / М. В. Асалханова // Царскосельские чтения. — 2014. — Вып. 18. — Т. I. Современные проблемы теории и истории искусства. — С. 161–164.
2. Боднарчук Т. В. Постмодерністські тенденції у сучасному українському мистецтві [Текст]: автореф. дис. ... канд. мистецтвознавства: 26.00.01 / Боднарчук Тетяна Валеріївна; Львів. нац. муз. акад. ім. М. В. Лисенка. — Львів, 2009. — 20 с.
3. Баженов В. Сергей Параджанов: встречи [Текст] / В. Баженов // Знамя. — 2015. — № 1. — С. 143–162.
4. Гучинова Э.-Б. Черное солнце и огороженный простор: образы неволи в творчестве Сергея Параджанова и Кадзуки Ясуо [Текст] / Эльза-Баир Гучинова // Comparative Studies on Regional. — 2013. — No. 12. Imagining the Landscape: Views from Armenia and Japan. — С. 45–58.
5. Катанян В. Параджанов. Цена вечного праздника [Текст] / Василий Катанян. — М.: Четыре искусства, 1994. — 205 с. — ISBN 5-7235-1218-8.

6. Кондахасзов Р. Незаконченные тетради. Фрагменты из книги воспоминаний [Заслуженный художник Грузии; восп. о С. Параджанове] [Текст] / Роберт Кондахасзов // Дружба Народов. — 2011. — № 9. — С. 169–189.
7. Оганесян М. Сергій Параджанов — геній, якого не зрозуміли [Текст] / Марго Оганесян (Київ), Іванка Грешлик (Прага) // Український журнал (Чехія). — 2007. — № 12. — С. 33–34.
8. Петрова О. С. Параджанов як граюча людина в контексті мистецтва трансавангарду [Текст] / Ольга Петрова // Петрова О. Мистецтвознавчі рефлексії. — К., 2004. — С. 72–75. — ISBN 978-966-518-236-6.
9. Саркисян З. Армения. Параджанов. Жизнь в коллажах [вспоминает директор дома-музея Сергея Параджанова (Ереван)] [Электронный ресурс] / Завен Саркисян. — Электрон. текстові дані і 1 відеозапис (18 хв. 53 сек.). — 2016. — 15 квітня. — Режим доступу: <http://glasweb.com/armeniya-paradzhanov-zhizn-v-kollazhah/> (дата звернення: 11.09.2018). — Назва з екрана.

References:

1. Asalkhanova, M. (2014). Kollazh kak iskusstvo: tekhnika, istoriia, khudozhniki [Collage as art: technology, history, artists]. *Tcarskoselskie chteniia*, 18 (1), 161–164. (In Russian).
2. Bodnarchuk, T. (2009). Postmodernistski tendentsii u suchasnomu ukrainskomu mystetstvi [Post-Modern Tendencies in Contemporary Ukrainian Art]. *Extended abstract of candidate's thesis*. Lviv. (In Ukrainian).
3. Bazhenov, V. (2015). Sergey Parajanov: vstrechi [Sergey Parajanov: Meetings]. *Znamia*, 1, 143–162. (In Russian).
4. Guchinova, E.-B. (2013). Chernoe solntce i ogorozhennyi prostor: obrazy nevoli v tvorchestve Sergeia Paradzhanova i Kadzuki Iasuo [The Black Sun and the Fenced Space: The Images of Captivity in the Works of Sergei Paradzhanov and Kazuki Yasuo]. *Comparative Studies on Regional*, 12, 45–58. (In Russian).
5. Katanyan, V. (1994). *Paradzhanov. Cena vechnogo prazdnika* [Parajanov. Price eternal holiday]. Moscow: Chetyre iskusstva. (In Russian).
6. Kondakhsazov, R. (2011). Nezakonchennyye tetradi. Fragmenty iz knigi vospominanii [Unfinished notebooks]. *Druzha Narodov*, 9, 169–189.
7. Ohanesian, M. & Greshlyk, I. (2007). Sergey Parajanov — henii, yakoho ne zrozumily [Sergey Parajanov — a genius who was not understood]. *Ukrainskyi zhurnal*, 12, 33–34. (In Ukrainian).
8. Petrova, O. (2004). S. Paradzhanov yak hraiuha liudyna v konteksti mystetstva transavanhardu [Sergiy Parajanov as a playing person in the context of transvanguard art]. In O. Petrova. *Mystetstvoznavchi refleksii*, (72–75). Kyiv. (In Ukrainian).
9. Sarkisyan, Z. (2016, April 15). Armeniya. Paradzhanov. Zhizn' v kollazhakh (vspominaet direktor doma-muzeya Sergeya Paradzhanova (Erevan)) [Armenia. Paradzhanov Life in collages]. *glasweb.com*. (Text & 1 video 18 min 53 sec). Retrieved from <http://glasweb.com/armeniya-paradzhanov-zhizn-v-kollazhah/>. (In Russian).

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